

METHODS, TECHNIQUES, AND TOOLS FOR DEVELOPING TEXT CREATION COMPETENCE IN PROSPECTIVE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

Khaitova Nodira

Doctoral student (PhD candidate) of Bukhara State Pedagogical
Institute

E-mail: nodiraxaitova21@gmail.com
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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the methods and techniques for developing text creation competence in prospective primary school teachers. Theoretical information about the methods and techniques that form text creation competence is provided, examples of them are given, and their practical significance is explained. The article also discusses the teacher's methodological preparation and pedagogical skills, and predicts the results achieved through the development of communicative competence and the effectiveness of learning activities.

Content.

Future primary school teachers must develop into well-qualified professionals who meet the demands of the labor market, establish their place in society, and become well-rounded specialists in their field while taking into account their professional needs. Today, this is a key requirement. In particular, primary education places great responsibility and high expectations on teachers. This is because, while providing education and upbringing to children, a primary school teacher must прежде all serve as a role model in every respect.

Children's developing speech, evolving thinking, and creative approach are directly influenced by the teacher's activity. Therefore, a teacher should possess pedagogical and communicative competencies and be able to meet modern educational requirements. Only when a future primary school teacher's oral and written speech is clear, fluent, and understandable can students grasp the material easily and quickly, and these skills will gradually develop in them as well. As a result, students' abilities to work with texts, express their ideas, and comprehend information are enhanced.

The effectiveness of pedagogical development requires a teacher to possess the following types of abilities:

1. **Cognitive ability.**
2. **Ability to explain clearly.**
3. **Observational ability.**
4. **Speech ability.**
5. **Organizational ability.**
6. **Ability to gain authority.**

7. **Ability to communicate appropriately.**

8. **Ability to foresee the future.**

9. **Ability to distribute attention.**

All of the above are closely related to a teacher's speech activity, and this is directly realized through the process of text production.

Developing the text-creation competence of future primary school teachers positively influences students' speech literacy, contributes to the effectiveness of lessons, and ensures high-quality learning outcomes. For this purpose, future educators should make comprehensive use of modern pedagogical approaches, effective methods, and various tools.

Below we analyze the approaches, methods, and tools that develop the text-creation competence of future primary school teachers.

1. **Approaches (methods).**

In active learning, students express their opinions, analyze, write, and participate in discussions.

The competency-based approach ensures that students acquire not only theoretical knowledge but also practical writing skills.

One of the most effective ways to develop both oral and written forms of text is the process of debate and discussion. Below, the types of these approaches and their significance are explained.

In the **heuristic approach**, one of the participants does not try to impose their solution to the problem directly; instead, they use persuasion, intuition, and common sense to influence others and guide them toward their point of view.

In the **logical approach**, the discussion is characterized by strong logical analysis and evidence-based arguments, through which participants arrive at well-founded conclusions.

In the **sophistic approach**, one side may defeat the opponent through cleverness or wisdom rather than purely factual argumentation.

In the **authoritarian approach**, one participant may rely on their authority or status to impose their viewpoint on others.

The **critical approach** involves participants who focus only on the weaknesses, limitations, or vulnerable points of their opponent, often ignoring the positive aspects of the opposing viewpoint and failing to offer constructive solutions to the problem.

In the **pragmatic approach**, participants do not engage in debate solely to establish truth; instead, they may steer the discussion toward their own hidden or practical interests, which may not be openly expressed to others involved in the debate.

2. **METHODS**

"Cluster" method

- Free generation of ideas on a given topic
- Helps in creating a structured plan for the text

"Brainstorming" method

- Encourages rapid idea generation
- Enriches the content of the text

"INSERT" method

- Deepens comprehension through reading and marking the text

- Serves as a basis for creating new texts **“Sinkveyn” method**

- Develops the skill of composing short and meaningful texts

“Role play” method

- Writing texts in various communicative situations (e.g., writing as a teacher addressing parents)

“Peer review” method

- Students analyze each other’s texts
- Develops critical thinking skills

3. TOOLS

Traditional tools

- Textbooks and учебные materials
- Methodological guidelines
- Dictionaries

Digital tools

- Google Docs – collaborative writing
- Grammarly – grammar checking
- Padlet – idea sharing
- Canva – creating visual texts

Didactic tools

- Text samples (essays, articles, annotations)
- Planning and structure templates
- Assessment criteria (rubrics)

To educate students as individuals who meet the demands of the modern era, it is first necessary to shape teachers accordingly. A well-developed and competent teacher personality is capable of nurturing a well-rounded generation.

The development of text-creation competence in future teachers requires the integration of interactive methods, practical activities, and digital tools. This process shapes them not only as proficient writers but also as effective communicators and qualified pedagogical professionals..

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